

Unresolved Trauma: Its Impact and Treatment

TEIBOWEI Bodisere Juliet, Ph.D

Department of Foundations, Arts and Social Science Education

Federal University Otuoke,

P. M. B. 126 Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

drbodiz2014@gmail.com

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Abstract

Trauma is an emotional response to a terrible event like an accident, rape, or natural disaster. Immediately after the event, shock and denial are typical. Longer term reactions include unpredictable emotions, flashbacks, strained relationships, and even physical symptoms like headaches or nausea, low academic performance, low self-esteem to mention a few. Trauma, if unresolved can have adverse effect on its victim. This paper explored unresolved trauma, its causes, symptoms, impact and treatment which includes Cognitive Behavior Therapy (CBT), Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR) and Supportive Psychotherapy (SP). Suggestions made include amongst others the provision of Counselling Units manned by Professional counselors in all schools and the need for enlightenment programmes through mass media to be carried out regularly by the State Ministries of Information.

Keywords: Unresolved Trauma, Emotional Response, Natural Disaster, Supportive Psychotherapy, and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

Introduction

In Nigeria, as in other parts of the world, humans are often faced with traumatic events that leave lasting impact on survivors. According to the United States Department of Human Services (2022), at least one in seven children is a victim of child maltreatment in a given year. In addition, two out of three children experience at least one traumatic event by age 16, including psychological, physical, sexual abuse or violence. Aside these, many persons experience other forms of traumatic events such as wars, terrorism, natural disasters, accidents etc.

Traumatic events are events or series of events that cause a lot of stress on victims. Traumatic event is an incident that causes physical, emotional, spiritual or psychological harm. The person experiencing the distressing event may feel physically threatened or extremely frightened as a result. In some cases, they may not know how to respond or may be in denial about the effect such an event has had. The person will need support and time to recover from the traumatic event and regain emotional and mental stability. Traumatic events are marked by a sense of horror, hopelessness, serious injury, or the stress of serious injury or death. After experiencing a traumatic event, survivors often experience trauma.

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There are three main types of trauma; acute, chronic and complex. Acute trauma results from a single incident, chronic trauma is repeated and prolonged such as domestic violence or abuse,

complex trauma is exposure to varied and multiple traumatic events, often of an invasive, interpersonal nature. This occurs from exposure to multiple and repetitive episodes of victimization or other traumatic events. Individuals who are exposed to multiple forms of trauma often display a wide range of difficulties compared to those who have one or few trauma exposures. For example, cognitive complications (dissociation), affective, somatic, behavioural, relational, and self-attributional problems have been seen in individuals who have experienced complex trauma (Peterson, 2017).

Trauma is a life-altering experience. Most traumatic events experienced during the early stages of life can affect one's entire lifespan. Childhood trauma is often described as serious adverse childhood experiences. Children may go through a range of experiences that classify as psychological trauma; these might include neglect, abandonment, sexual abuse, emotional abuse, and physical abuse, witnessing abuse of a sibling or parent, or having a mentally ill parent. These events have profound psychological, physiological, and sociological impacts and can have negative, lasting effects on health and well-being such as anti-social behaviours, attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD), and sleep disturbances. Similarly, children with mothers who have experienced traumatic or stressful events during pregnancy can increase the child's risk of mental health disorders and other neuro-developmental disorders (Wikipedia, 2023).

Kaiser Permanente and the Centers for Disease Control and Preventions 1988 study on adverse childhood experiences determined that traumatic experiences during childhood are a root cause of many social, emotional, and cognitive impairments that lead to increased risk of unhealthy self-destructive behaviours, risk of violence or re-victimization, chronic health conditions, low life potential and premature mortality. As the number of adverse experiences increases, the risk of problems from childhood through adulthood also increases. The impact of childhood traumatic stress can last well beyond childhood. In fact, research has shown that trauma survivors may experience:

- i. Learning problems, including lower grades and more suspensions.
- ii. Increased use of health and mental services.
- iii. Increased involvement with child welfare and juvenile justice.
- iv. Long-term health problems (for example, diabetes and heart disease).

Trauma is a risk factor for nearly all behavioural health and substance use disorders. All these can interfere with normal functioning of the individual all through life if the trauma is not resolved.

Unresolved trauma occurs when the person has experienced an overwhelming event or series of events outside their brain's window of tolerance. The survivor protects themselves from the pain by repressing and avoiding the disturbing emotions and trying to get over the trauma by pushing it down (Zackson, 2022). The neglected past trauma can have a large effect on one's future health. The psychological and physical responses it triggers can make one susceptible to severe health conditions including stroke, heart attack, weight problems, diabetes, and cancer (Harvard Medical School, 2020).

Unresolved trauma arises when stressed or something in the person's life serves as a barely perceptible or not-so-subtle reminder of what occurred when the victim was young. Childhood experience is reflected in symptoms such as depression, panic attacks, eating problems, obsessive thoughts, catastrophic worries, relationship concerns, trust issues, low self-esteem, fears of being judged, outbursts of anger, social anxiety, frequent attempts to please people, etc.

Unresolved trauma puts people at increased risk of mental health diagnoses, which run the gamut of anxiety, depression and PTSD. There are physical manifestations as well, such as cardiovascular

problems like high blood pressure, stroke or heart attacks. The effects of unresolved trauma can be devastating. It can affect one's habits and outlook on life, leading to addiction and poor decision-making. Studies suggest that unresolved trauma could make one more vulnerable to developing both physical and mental health problems (Gupta, 2022, Teibowei & Balogun, 2022). According to World Health Organization (WHO), (2012), mental health is 'a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stress of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community. Mental health is how one feels about oneself and others, able to meet the demands of life and to develop psychologically and emotionally. Being mentally healthy is having the strength to overcome the difficulties and challenges the person can face at times, to have confidence and self-esteem, to be able to take decisions and to believe in oneself (Ruch, 2018). Mental health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being. Mental health includes emotional, psychological and social well-being. It affects how a person thinks, feels, and acts. It also helps determine how one handles stress, relate to others, and make choices. Mental health is important at every stage of life, from childhood and adolescence through adulthood. It is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease (WHO, 2012). Adi (2020), opined that feelings of well-being are fundamental to the overall health of an individual, enabling one to successfully overcome difficulties and achieve what one wants out of life. Past experiences, attitudes and outlook can all impact well-being as can physical or emotional trauma following specific events.

Causes of Unresolved Trauma

One of the first things to understand about unresolved trauma is that there's no set cause-and-effect relationship. There are many different types of trauma and each person's reaction to the event depends upon a host of factors, such as whether the person was able to 'process' the event with the right support systems. However, there are some common events that constitute trauma such as:

- i. Childhood sexual or physical abuse
- ii. Witnessing domestic violence
- iii. Bullying
- iv. Community or school violence
- v. Natural disasters
- vi. Loss of a loved one
- vii. Neglect
- viii. Serious illness or accident

These are common examples of trauma, some events not listed here can still be traumatic for some persons (Rauch and Foa, 2016).

Symptoms of Unresolved Trauma

Some of the symptoms of unresolved trauma as opined by Zackson (2022) and Teibowei (2019) are:

1. Anxiety or panic attacks that occur in what would be considered normal situations.
2. A feeling of shame; an innate feeling that they are bad, worthless, or without importance.
3. Suffering from chronic or ongoing depression.
4. Practicing avoidance of people, places, or things that may be related to the traumatic event; this also can include an avoidance of unpleasant emotions.

5. Flashbacks, nightmares, and body memories regarding the traumatic event.
6. Addiction and eating disorders in an attempt to escape or numb negative emotions.
7. Suffering from feelings of detachment, or feelings of ‘dead inside’ (This is perhaps the most devastating of the signs, because it creates a feeling of loneliness and isolation).
8. Sleeping issues including trouble going to sleep or staying awake.
9. Hyper-vigilance and inability to let one’s own guard down.
10. Lack of trust and difficulty opening up to other people.
11. Dissociation and a persistent feeling of numbness.
12. Control issues, to overcompensate for feeling helpless during the traumatic incident.
13. Low self-esteem and feelings of worthlessness.
14. Uncontrollable anger; acting on it.
15. Suicidal thoughts for actions.
16. Self-harm, cutting, and mutilation.
17. Not being able to tolerate conflicts as they once would have.
18. Unexplained or irrational fears of people, places, or things

Impact of Unresolved Trauma

There are many ways in which the lingering effects of unresolved trauma can impact one’s life. As an adult, feelings of anxiety, worry, shame, guilt, sadness and anger that started with a trauma in childhood can continue. In addition, those who endure trauma as a child are more likely to encounter anxiety, depression, suicide and self-harm, PTSD, drug and alcohol misuse and relationship difficulties. The effects of unresolved trauma do not end with just emotional repercussions. Survivors are at higher risk of developing asthma, coronary disease, diabetes or having a stroke. They are also more likely to develop a ‘heightened stress response’ which can make it difficult for them to regulate their emotions, lead to sleep difficulties, lower immune function, and increase the risk of a number of physical illnesses throughout adulthood.

Unresolved trauma can leave epigenetic marks on a child’s genes, which chemically modify gene expression by silencing or activating genes. This can alter fundamental biological processes and adversely affect health outcomes throughout life.

Survivors of war trauma or childhood maltreatment are at increased risk for trauma-spectrum disorders such as PTSD. In addition, traumatic stress has been associated with alterations in the neuro-endocrine and the immune system, enhancing the risk for physical diseases. In particular, epigenetic alterations in genes regulating the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal axis as well as the immune system have been observed in survivors of childhood and adult trauma. Others include:

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

Posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) is a psychiatric disorder that may occur in people who have experienced or witnessed a traumatic event, series of events or set of circumstances. An individual may experience this as emotionally or physically harmful or life-threatening and may affect mental, physical, social and or spiritual well-being. Examples include natural disasters, serious accidents, terrorist acts, war/combat, rape/sexual assault, historical trauma, intimate, intimate partner violence and bullying.

People with PTSD have intense, disturbing thoughts and feelings related to their experience that last long after the traumatic event has ended. They may relive the event through flashbacks or nightmares, they may feel sadness, fear or anger, and they may feel detached or estranged from

other people. They may avoid situations that remind them of the traumatic event, and they may have strong negative reactions to something as ordinary as a loud noise or an accidental touch.

1. Reliving the event (flashbacks or nightmares)
2. Avoidance
3. Anxiety
4. Depression
5. Anger
6. Problems with trust
7. Self-destructive or risky behavior
8. Withdrawal

Attachment and Relationships

Attachment describes how early relationships with a primary caregiver, most commonly a parent, creates expectations for how love should be. One's view of self and others is molded by how well these caregivers were available and responsive to meet one's physical and emotional needs. Unresolved trauma results in problems forming attachments and relationships. For example, if the trauma was caused by a loved one or caregiver, the victim may learn to mistrust adults. This mistrust can be carried over into adulthood and affect the person's ability to form relationships with others, or consistently form unhealthy relationships with people with undesirable behaviours. Whatever the case, the person forms unhealthy relationships with peers.

Emotional Regulation and Responses

Emotional regulation or emotion regulation is the ability to respond to the ongoing demands of experience with the range of emotions in a manner that is socially tolerable and sufficiently flexible to permit spontaneous reactions as well as the ability to delay spontaneous reactions as needed (Wikipedia, 2023). It is the ability to exert control over one's own emotional state. It may involve behaviours such as rethinking a challenging situation to reduce anger or anxiety, hiding visible signs of sadness or fear, or focusing on reasons to feel happy or calm. Emotional response is an emotional reaction, such as happiness, fear or sadness, to a given stimulus. For persons who are victims of unresolved trauma, the emotional responses are mostly negative especially in situations similar to the traumatic event they suffered. There are many ways in which this can manifest which includes:

- i. uncontrollable anger
- ii. anxiety
- iii. depression
- iv. inability to express emotions
- v. withdrawal

Physical Health

Physical health is a state of health and well-being and, more specifically, the ability to perform optimally. It is the condition of the body, taking into consideration everything from the absence of disease to fitness level. Physical health is critical for overall well-being, and can be affected by lifestyles; diet, level of physical activity, behavior and past events. Unresolved trauma affects physical health, studies have shown that children who were subjected to abuse were more at risk for serious health issues, including:

- i. diabetes
- ii. coronary artery disease
- iii. asthma
- iv. stroke

Suicide attempts are also shown to be considerably higher among adults who experienced childhood trauma (Zackson, 2022, Teibowei, 2019, United Nations, 2014).

Treatment

Most people recover naturally from trauma but it can take time. There are three main types of talking therapies used to treat people with unresolved trauma. These are:

1. Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT)

Cognitive behaviour therapy (CBT) is a type of talking therapy that aims to help one manage problems by changing how people think and act. It is a type of psychotherapeutic treatment that helps people learn how to identify and change the destructive or disturbing thought patterns that have a negative influence on their behaviour and emotions (Benight and Bandura, 2004).

Cognitive behavioural therapy combines cognitive therapy with behaviour therapy by identifying maladaptive patterns of thinking, emotional responses, or behaviours and replacing them with more desirable patterns. Cognitive behavioural therapy focuses on changing the automatic negative thoughts that can contribute to and worsen one's emotional difficulties, depression, and anxiety. These spontaneous negative thoughts also have a detrimental influence on our mood. Through CBT, faulty thoughts are identified, challenged, and replaced with more objective, realistic thoughts.

CBT encompasses a range of techniques and approaches that address our thoughts, emotions, and behaviors. These can range from structured psychotherapies to self-help practices. Some of the specific types of therapeutic approaches that involve cognitive behavioral therapy include:

- i. Cognitive therapy centers on identifying and changing inaccurate or distorted thought patterns, emotional responses, and behaviors.
- ii. Dialectical behavior therapy (DBT) addresses destructive or disturbing thoughts and behaviors while incorporating treatment strategies such as emotional regulation and mindfulness.
- iii. Multimodal therapy suggests that psychological issues must be treated by addressing seven different but interconnected modalities: behavior, affect, sensation, imagery, cognition, interpersonal factors, and drug/biological considerations.
- iv. Rational emotive behavior therapy (REBT) involves identifying irrational beliefs, actively challenging these beliefs, and finally learning to recognize and change these thought patterns (Rauch and Foa, 2006).

While each type of cognitive behavioral therapy takes a different approach, all work to address the underlying thought patterns that contribute to psychological distress and are effective for the treatment of trauma.

Using CBT to Treat Trauma

CBT targets current problems and is typically delivered in 12 – 16 sessions in either individual or group format consisting of phases which are:

1. Assessment and Engagement

The initial phase designed to provide assessment and engagement, including the development of a problem list, establishment of shared goals and the collaborative development of a maintenance formulation of a recent incident.

2. Understanding your thoughts

The therapist guides the client to learn to understand and control his or her thoughts. The therapist might spend some time with the client with understanding events in their past. CBT does not focus on the past. To help a client understand the past, it is necessary to help them understand their present through processed thoughts.

3. Working with your Behaviour

The therapist guides clients to learn to understand how their thoughts and behavior influence each other. The client establishes pattern of thought and behaviour that helps him manage his symptoms. Between therapy sessions, the client usually perform activities that are related to the new patterns.

4. Being your own Therapist

Towards the end of the CBT treatment, the client usually becomes prepared to stop therapy and deal with the symptoms himself. In essence, the therapy does not stop with the therapist, the client continues the treatment on his own, the client becomes his own therapist (Peterson, 2017).

2. Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR)

Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR) is a structured therapy that encourages the patient to briefly focus on the trauma memory while simultaneously experiencing bilateral stimulation (typically eye movements), which is associated with a reduction in the vividness and emotion associated with the trauma memories.

EMDR therapy (Shapiro, 2007) was initially developed in 1987 for the treatment of posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and is guided by the Adaptive Information Processing model (Shapiro, 2007). It is an individual therapy typically delivered one to two times per week for a total of 6-12 sessions, although some people benefit from fewer sessions. Sessions can be conducted on consecutive days.

The Adaptive Information Processing model considers symptoms of PTSD and other disorders (unless physically or chemically based) to result from past disturbing experiences that continue to cause distress because the memory was not adequately processed. These unprocessed memories are understood to contain the emotions, thoughts, beliefs and physical sensations that occurred at the time of the event. When the memories are triggered, these stored disturbing elements are experienced and cause the symptoms of PTSD and/or other disorders (Grey, 2019, Teibowei and Osusu, 2018).

Unlike other treatments that focus on directly altering the emotions, thoughts and responses resulting from traumatic experiences, EMDR therapy focuses directly on the memory, and is intended to change the way that the memory is stored in the brain, thus reducing and eliminating the problematic symptoms.

During EMDR therapy, clinical observations suggest that an accelerated learning process is stimulated by EMDR's standardized procedures, which incorporate the use of eye movements and other forms of rhythmic left-right (bilateral) stimulation (e.g., tones or taps). While clients briefly focus on the trauma memory and simultaneously experience bilateral stimulation (BLS), the vividness and emotion of the memory are reduced (Ehlers, 2013)

Closure

Closure is used to end the session. If the targeted memory was not fully processed in the session, specific instructions and techniques are used to provide containment and ensure safety until the next session.

Re-evaluation

The next session starts with phase eight, re-evaluation, during which the therapist evaluates the client's current psychological state, whether treatment effects have maintained, what memories may have emerged since the last session, and works with the client to identify targets for the current session.

3. Supportive Psychotherapy (SP)

Supportive psychotherapy is a type of therapy that primarily focuses on providing emotional support, encouragement, and validation during difficult life circumstances or psychological challenges. It relies on therapeutic alliance to alleviate symptoms, improve self-esteem, restore relation to reality, regulate impulses and negative thinking, and reinforce the ability to cope with life stressors and challenges. The therapist encourages the client to talk about his feelings, concerns, and problems in a safe, nonjudgmental environment. The therapist also renders advice to the client aimed at reducing client-distress without specifically addressing the psychological and behavioural causes. Thus, supportive procedures are non-specific in nature (Monsoon and Shnaider, 2004).

Conclusion

Traumatic events are part and parcel of human existence as humans are always faced with challenges, experiences and unpleasant events that leave lasting pains and scars that never heal except where deliberate efforts are made to deal with such. The pains and scars left by the unpleasant events most times interfere with the normal functioning of the individual in more ways than one. The present paper explored the impact and treatment of unresolved. The study reveals that unresolved trauma has negative impact on victims both physically, socially, academically, psychologically, mentally and also on peoples' health. The study therefore, concludes that victims must undergo treatment so as to lead well-adjusted lives and be more useful to themselves and society.

Suggestions

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are presented for implementation;

1. Provision of Counselling Units manned by Professional counselors in all schools.
2. Government should establish Counselling and Human development centres in all local government areas.
3. Government should employ and deploy mental health counsellors to all establishments to enable them carry out programmes that would provide regular medical examination, mental health care and counselling services to staffs on regular basis.
4. Enlightenment programmes through mass media should be carried out regularly by the State Ministry.

5. Counselling Association of Nigeria in collaboration with non-governmental organizations, Community-based Organizations and Faith-based Organizations carry out sensitization programmes from time to time.

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